

OPTIMISING
ENERGY USE IN
CITIES THROUGH
SMART DECISION
SUPPORT SYSTEMS

FP7/608703

Functional end-user web-based

Deliverable number D3.4

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Preface

This report is prepared within the framework of the OPTIMUS – OPTIMising the energy USE in cities with smart decision support system (OPTIMUS) (608703), supported by the 7th Framework Programme, under the Objective ICT-2013.6.4 Optimising Energy Systems in Smart Cities. OPTIMUS aims to design, develop and implementation a Decision Support System (DSS) addressed to city authorities, in order to assist them to optimize the energy use in their premises and reduce CO₂ emissions.

Summary

This deliverable refers to task 3.4 of the project. This task has the purpose of developing the web-based environments which facilitate end-users the interaction with the OPTIMUS DSS according to their requirements and knowledge.

This document presents the environments of the OPTIMUS DSS and the technical details of their implementation. The outcomes of this task have been three environments:

- DSS end-user web environment. It is the front end of the DSS where the users are able to understand the suggestions offered by the DSS and react to them.
- The DSS management environment. It is the back office of the DSS where the technicians can setup and fine tune the components of the DSS.
- The DSS data portal environment. The monitored data is published through the data portal to be reused by citizens and third parties.

The environments have been designed with the collaboration of the end-users by means of surveys and mock-ups that started to be developed in Task 1.3. Several iterations have been carried out with end-users to discuss with them the successive versions of the interfaces.

The environments are open and flexible in order to be installed in cities, other than the pilot ones, in the future. This might bring other buildings, sensors, action plans, and languages.

Deliverable structure

The document is divided into three main sections: the first one contains the formulation of the design decisions, the second section contains the description of the DSS end-user front-ends and management environments, and the third section presents the data portal environment.

The design decisions are structured according to the following sub-sections:

- Elements of the environments. A description of the main elements considered in the environments and how they are related with the DSS modules carried out in other tasks of the WP3.
- Prediction models and action plan calculations. A description of the rationale behind the calculation of the forecasted data and the action plans. It is explained how the outputs of those calculations are used in the environments.

The DSS end-user web and management environment section is structured according to the following sub-sections:

- Environments layouts. The layout of both environments –front-end and management– since they share the same layout.
- Sitemap of the DSS environments. The sitemap of the environments which includes the navigation among different web pages.
- End-user web environment. The web pages of environment including the interfaces of the action plans.
- Management environment. The web pages of the management environment which are used to setup the DSS and manage the elements such as sensors, buildings, and partitions.

The data portal environment section describes the implementation of the data portal using the ELDA system. It includes examples of how the data is presented to the user and the different formats used to return the data.

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1 Introduction

This document summarises the outcomes of Task 3.4 *Front-end environments* as part of WP3 *Semantic Data Integration and Development of OPTIMUS DSS*. The purpose of this task is to create the web-based environments which will facilitate end-users the interaction with the OPTIMUS DSS according to their requirements and knowledge. These environments have been designed according to the specifications gathered in Task 1.3 *User Requirements*.

The development of the environments started in Task 1.3 with the creation of the mock-ups of the interfaces. The mock-ups were produced in collaboration with the end-users. This way, they facilitated the identification of the requirements of the DSS in each pilot case. Once the mock-ups were agreed, the environments have been developed according to them. Finally, the environments have been validated with the end-users.

One of the main requirements of the DSS environments is that they should be open and flexible in order to be installed in other cities in the future.

The outcomes of this task have been the following:

- **DSS end-user web environment.** It is the front-end of the DSS where the users are able to understand the suggestions offered by the DSS and react to them. Different kinds of visualizations have been implemented to visualise the current performance of the buildings as well as to display the action plans suggested by the DSS.
- **DSS management environment.** It is the back office of the DSS where the technicians can setup and fine tune the components of the DSS.
- **DSS data portal environment.** The data captured by the WP2 modules is published through the data portal to be reused by citizens and third parties.

1.1 Interconnection between Tasks

The work carried out in Task 3.4 is related to other tasks in the following way:

- The user requirements started to be captured in Task 1.3 by means of surveys and mock-ups which have been used to design the end-user web environment.
- The environments carried out in Task 3.4 *Front-end Environments* are contextualized in Task 3.5 *Integration and Development of OPTIMUS DSS* where the integration of the different modules of the DSS and the relations among modules, is explained.
- The environments are the interface to display the results of the action plans calculations using inference rules. Those rules are formulated and explained in Deliverable 3.3 *Inference Engine Integrated in the Management Environments*.
- The environments display forecasted data which is calculated with the prediction models explained in deliverable 3.2.

The data portal shares the monitored data collected through the semantic framework described in Deliverable 3.1 *Published Data in an Open Data Portal*.

2 Design decisions

The DSS environments have been designed according to the specifications derived from the user requirements captured in Task 1.3. The design of the environments takes into account that the DSS can be expanded in the future as new cities, buildings, sensors and actions plans are aggregated to it. For a given city, the environments need to facilitate the setting up of new sensors in the existing buildings and also the addition of new buildings.

The interfaces have been designed to be multi-lingual, so that they can be customize to the languages used in the pilot cities (e.g., Spanish, Catalan, Italian, Dutch), keeping English as the default language. Adding a new language to the interfaces should be an easy task that non-technical users will be able to do filling only a text file.

2.1 Elements of the environments

The main components of the OPTIMUS DSS are sensors, buildings, partitions, predictions, action plans, and action plan outputs (Figure 1). A building has partitions such as floors, sections, rooms among others. The partitions are related between them in a hierarchical way. For example, a building has floors which have sections, and the sections have in turn rooms. The partitions are monitored by sensors such as temperature or humidity sensors. When a sensor monitors the whole building, such as the outdoor temperature sensor, it is related to the root partition. A sensor is a device that monitors something. It might be related to a physical device installed in the building. The sensors send data through the semantic framework to the DSS in RDF format. The sensors are identified by a specific URI¹.

The Action Plans proposed by the DSS are applied to a specific partition and have a predefined set of input variables. For example, the Action Plan “Scheduling the PV maintenance” needs: energy production, energy consumption and energy prices. These variables can be fed with monitored data or with predicted data.

The predicted data is calculated with the prediction models using the historical and monitored data from the sensors. The prediction models (developed in Task 3.2 *Data Mining Analysis*) have data from the sensors –through the Semantic Framework (developed in Task 3.1 *Semantic Framework for Data Integration*) – and forecast building behaviour for the next 7 days. The predicted data is stored in the database.

The Action Plans generate the outputs using the input variables and some static data. The outputs of the calculations of an Action Plan are stored in the database in specific tables for each action plan (see database structure in Section 3.5.2). An Action Plan can be applied to any building partition. To do so, the sensors are mapped to the input variables needed for the action plan in a specific partition.

¹ For example: http://www.optimus-smartcity.eu/resource/sant_cugat/sensingdevice/sunnyportal_energy_production

Figure 1: Components of the DSS and their relations

2.2 Prediction models and action plans calculation

The prediction models are invoked every day at night for each variable that is required by an Action Plan. The predictions have a time horizon of seven days. In this way, each day, a prediction for the following seven days is carried out. Predictions are not stored in a triple-store (used for real monitored data), but in the environments database. This is because of their variability. In this way, users can create predictions in the past, for example, for testing purposes.

Action Plans are pre-calculated just after the predictions have been carried out. In this way, users can visualize the output of the plans and the monitored data with a short time response. The plans use the data from the last prediction.

Figure 2: Predicted data and Action Plans calculation

Figure 2 displays the prediction and action plans calculations in operation. On Sunday night, for example, a calculation of the next seven days' forecast is invoked (orange dashed line). This prediction uses the previous monitored data (in grey solid line). For each day, the Action

Plans are calculated (orange circles) with the last prediction data from Monday to the next Sunday. Afterwards, on Monday, another forecast calculation is invoked at night (blue dashed line). The plans are again calculated but with the new prediction from Tuesday to the next Monday (blue circles). Finally, on Tuesday a forecast calculation is invoked (green dashed line). The plans are calculated with the last prediction from Wednesday to the next Tuesday (green circles). In this manner, a user who is analysing the performance of one week is able to see seven action plans, calculated with three different prediction data.

3 DSS End-user web and management environment

The end-user and management environments are part of a unique environment even though they are reported separately in this document. The reason to bring them together is that both environments are strongly intertwined. This is because the management environment is used to setup and tune the end-user web environment. The data portal environment, however, is completely separated from the other two.

3.1 Environments layout

Both environments, end-user and management, share the same layout. In this way the learning curve for users is less difficult (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Interface layout

In the header, users find the name of the DSS and the name of the city. On the left side, there is the user information which includes the name of the user and the log out option. Below the user information, there is a section for the highlighted elements which can be a city or a particular building. Below the panel of the highlighted element there is the activity stream which displays the activity of the DSS such as system events (e.g., new calculations, alarms...) and user events (e.g., acceptance of an action plane).

On the top of the right side of the layout, there is the bread crumb which helps to navigate through the interfaces. An example of a bread crumb for an Action Plan page would be: "Sant Cugat > Town Hall > Action plan: scheduling of the sale/consumption of the electricity produced through the PV system". Each of the texts between '>' character is a link to access the

corresponding page. Below the bread crumb, there is the main content section. This section is related to the content of the current page. For example, in the city page, a list of buildings will be displayed in the main content section. However, in the Action Plan page, the suggested action and some monitored and forecasted data will be shown.

3.2 Sitemap of the DSS environments

Figure 4 shows the sitemap of both environments. Depending on the role of the user, the management environment is enabled or not. The blue boxes are the pages of the end-user environment and the green boxes are the pages of the management environment. The first page access by the user is “home”. This is where the user can log in. If the role of the user is “administrator” then it is possible to access the management pages. Otherwise the access is restricted to the end-user pages.

Figure 4: Sitemap of the DSS end-user and management environments

3.3 End-user web environment

This is the main environment of the DSS and its purpose is to support the decision making processes of the users. The user of this environment is an energy manager, responsible for one or several public buildings. Monitored and forecasted data is presented to the user and the suggested Action Plans generated from the intelligent rules using the predicted data. Different plans can be applied in each building to optimise different indicators such as the use of renewable energy, energy cost, energy consumption, among others.

3.3.1 City dashboard

After logging in, a screen shows the current status of the monitored buildings as well as the suggested Action Plans to increase the energy efficiency of the buildings (Figure 5). Key performance indicators –such as total energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, renewable generation, and electrical power among others–, are shown in the right panel. The data reflecting the user activity in the last seven days is also displayed (plans accepted, declined, and inactivity). This data is aggregated for all the buildings of the city.

Every building is described by its general attributes such as building use, address, year of construction, surface, number of floors, and occupation. In addition, global energy indicators are listed: energy rating, renewable generation, thermal power, and energy consumption. Finally, real time data –such as outdoor and indoor temperature, renewable generation, energy consumption and CO₂ emissions–, is displayed.

With regard to the Action Plans, for each building it is shown when an action was performed and the status of the plans (e.g., no action required, action required).

Figure 5: End-user web environment: City dashboard

3.3.2 Selected building. Dashboard

Once the user selects a building, a dashboard shows the list of the available Action Plans – including their status– and the actual performance of the building in terms of energy production, energy consumption, energy cost and CO₂ emissions (Figure 6). It is also shown statistics with regard the user activity (action plans accepted, declined, and inactivity) for the last seven days.

Figure 6: End-user web environment: Building dashboard

3.3.3 Selected building. Historical and forecasted data

The user can see the monitored data by clicking on the historical and forecasted data chart, in the dashboard. Here, the user can see the monitored data that are relevant to understand the behaviour of the building (Figure 7).

Figure 7: End-user web environment: Historical and forecasted data.

3.3.4 Selected building. Action plan: Scheduling of the Sale/Consumption of the RES Electricity Produced

The user can visualize the Action Plans proposed by the DSS by clicking on their name. Figure 8 shows the plan “Scheduling of the Sale/Consumption of the RES Electricity Produced”. In this plan the end-user can see the forecasted energy/water consumption and the RES production for the following seven days. For each day, the DSS proposes an action with regard to the energy produced in the building. For example, it can suggest to sell the energy surplus, or to consume the energy to satisfy the energy demand of a building. The actions are suggested according to the type of strategy that is selected: “Finance”, “Green”, or “Intermediate”. At the bottom of the table, users choose whether they have accepted the recommendation provided by the system or not.

Figure 8: Action Plan: Scheduling of the Sale/Consumption of the RES Electricity Produced.

3.3.5 Selected building. Action plan: PV Maintenance

This Action Plan notifies users about the renewable energy production performance to check if there is a problem with the equipment (e.g. Photovoltaic Panels). The alarm is raised when there is a significant difference between the energy that the equipment should produce according to predicted values. With this purpose, the difference between the produced energy as compared to the values that are predicted by the DSS is shown in a table (Figure 9). Alerts are triggered to notify end-users when an anomaly is detected after analysing deviations exceeding 5% over a consecutive period of time. Inputs of possible alerts in the interface are provided by a web service for each day. Afterwards, a message is shown in the bottom of the table for each day: "OK" (in green colour) if there is no problem or "ALERT PWR" (in red colour), otherwise. Total values (historical and predicted values for production and solar radiation) are shown for each day.

Figure 9: Action Plan: PV Maintenance.

3.3.6 Selected building. Action plan: Optimum Start/Stop of the Heating/Cooling System

This Action Plan enables end-users to optimize the boost time of the heating/cooling systems taking into account the occupancy of the building, the weather forecast and the outdoor temperature. The interface shows the start/stop times for the air conditioning equipment in a certain building zone. This information is visualized according to the building configuration — by the user of the management environment—, which is divided in zones and floors, for each day in a week. The starting day can be selected through a date-picker. Four values are shown for each machine: current cooling/heating schedule values (in Figure 10, rows with title in orange show the baseline) and the predicted ones (in Figure 10, rows with title in green). Since a large amount of information can be displayed, the interface allows users to visualize the data type in which they could be more interested (cooling, heating or baseline values). Total values of saving energy and CO₂ emissions are shown for each day.

Figure 10: Action Plan: Optimum Start/Stop of the Heating/Cooling System.

3.4 Management environment

The user of the management environment is a technician who knows about the building's operation and knows how OPTIMUS DSS work. The purpose of this environment is to help the administrator to configure the DSS to suit the characteristics of the monitored buildings.

After logging in the management environment a screen shows the available buildings and a list of possible actions: adding a new building, editing an existing building, and removing buildings (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Management environment: Home

The configuration of a building includes setting up the building partitions, sensors, and Action Plans.

In the building partitions view, the user can specify the subdivision of the building space into floors, sections and rooms (Figure 12). The Action Plans will be constrained to a particular spatial element. For example, a user can perform an plan which conveys turning on/off the heating system in every floor.

Figure 12: Management environment: Building partitions

A list of sensors installed in a building is shown in Figure 13. The configuration of the sensors in the management environment is related to the configuration of the semantic framework described in Deliverable 3.1.

Figure 13: Management environment: Sensors

Action Plans can be configured for each building. A list of available plans is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Management environment: Action Plans

Action Plans are setup for each building partition. The configuration of a plan includes linking sensors to a certain partition (Figure 15). Every plan requires of different types of sensors that could provide the input data. For example, in the “scheduling of the sale/consumption of the electricity produced through the PV system” plan, the data that is needed is energy consumption, energy production and energy price.

Figure 15: Management environment: Action Plan setup

3.5 Development of the environments

The environments have been developed as a PHP web application using the Symfony framework. This solution has been adopted to speed up the creation and maintenance of web applications and to avoid repetitive coding tasks. The framework follows the model-view-

controller pattern. That is, the user interacts with a controller that manipulates the model. Later, the model updates the view which is visualized by the user.

The model interacts with the database of the environments and with the triple-store which has the monitored data (See Deliverable 3.5 for further information).

3.5.1 Web application structure

Symfony provides a fixed structure and folders that a web application has to follow. The main components of a Symfony application are:

- **Controllers:** They provide the basic functionality of the web pages that belong to the environments. They process the user requests. Usually a single controller manages one web page (login, users, actions plans...).
- **Entities:** They facilitate the mapping between the database and the Symfony application. Each table has an entity with the getters and setters to insert, update and remove entities.
- **Views:** These are the front-ends of the application. Every page is a view.
- **Services:** These are the main scripts that handle the data and process it to send it to the views. It contains the business logic. The Action Plans are coded as services.

The complete structure of the application is the following:

```

/app
  /config
    - config.yml: Configuration file of the application (users, parameters, languages...).
    - routing.yml: Bundle registration.
    - parameters.yml: Database configuration.
  /Resources
    /views/
      - base.html.twig: Basic HTML layout, it contains the header of the environments
front-end.
/src
  /Optimus/OptimusBundle/
    /Controller (All controllers)
      - AdminActionPlanController: functions for the administration of the action plans.
      - APSensorsController: functions for mapping sensors to action plan.
      - BuildingController: functions for managing a building.
      - InitController: methods for managing the initial web pages (init, login...).
      - LoginController: Methods for managing user management.
      - PartitionController: Methods for managing partition management
      - PredictionController: Methods for creating the charts of the historic & prediction
page.
      - SensorController: Methods for managing sensors.
      - PVActionPlanController: Methods for the PV Action Plan.
      - SwitchActionPlanController: Methods for the preheating/precooling Action Plan.

  /Entity
    - a list of entities for each table of the database.
  /Form
    - a list of forms for each entity.

```

/Repository

- *Advanced methods for handling the database access.*

/Resources

/config/

- **routing.yml**: *route declaration.*
- **services.yml**: *service declaration.*

/translations/

- *files with the different translations.*

/views/

- *views of the application.*

/Services

- **GestorOntologia**: *Methods for retrieving data from Virtuoso.*
- **GestorInvoke**: *Methods for invoke RapidAnalytics services (Prediction models).*
- **GestorCalculos**: *Methods for invoking the prediction models and the action*

plans.

- **GestorDataCapturing**: *Methods for obtaining the data needed for creating*

charts.

- **GestorEventos**: *Methods for logging the events (user actions).*
- **GestorAPPV**: *Methods for the PV action plan.*
- **GestorAPPreheating**: *Methods for the Pre-heating action plan.*
- **GestorAPAdaptative**: *Methods for the Adaptive comfort action plan.*
- **GestorAPTSV**: *Methods for the TSV action plan.*

/web/

/bundles/

/optimus/

/css

/js

/img

/files

3.5.2 Database structure

The environments use a database to store the static data related to the buildings and the settings needed to carry out the Action Plans. The forecasted data generated by the prediction models are also stored in the database. Figure 16 shows the database structure including the main tables with their columns (tables) and the relationships between them (lines between boxes).

Figure 16: Structure of the database

The main tables are the following:

- **Building:** Building basic properties.
- **ActionPlans:** List of action plans. The action plans are pre-defined in the environments. This table is used to enable/disable them (status).
- **BuildingPartitioning:** Partitions of the buildings. A partition can have other partitions. It follows a tree structure.
- **Prediction:** Predictions for a building. It has two dates, the date of the time period to create the prediction and the specific date and time when the prediction was generated. In this way a prediction could be carried out in the past for testing purposes.
- **RegisterPredictions:** For each prediction, the values are stored for all active sensors.
- **Sensor:** List of sensors, the Virtuoso server can be queried to check if the sensor is sending data or not, via the URI of the sensor.
- **Users:** List of users.

- **APCalculation:** Record of the calculations of the Action Plans for a specific date.
- **APSensors:** Mappings between sensors and partitions for a particular action plan.
- **APPVOutput:** Specific table of the PV Action Plan. It stores the values needed for the calculations.
- **APPVOutputDay:** Specific table of the PV Action Plan. It stores the inputs of the user for each day (strategy and status: accept, decline...).
- **APSwitchOutput:** Specific table for preheating action plan. It stores the values needed for the calculations.

4 Data portal environment

The purpose of the data portal environment is to publish the data collected by the data capturing modules developed in WP2 *Data Sources & Architecture of OPTIMUS DSS*. The data portal environment exposes monitored data in accordance with Linked Open Data principles. That is, the data is available in different formats such as HTML pages for human navigation, and machine-processable formats such as XML and RDF for agents and services. Citizens and third-parties can obtain the data in the portal for the development of their businesses.

The data portal environment has been implemented using ELDA², a Java implementation of the Linked Data API specification. It provides a configurable way to access RDF data using simple RESTful URLs that are translated into queries to the SPARQL endpoint of the Virtuoso endpoint.

The setup of an ELDA instance is a customized configuration file that includes parameters such as the SPARQL endpoints, the list of data which can be retrieved, and the styles of the visualization.

Figure 17 shows a list of the available sensors in the Sant Cugat data portal environment. In the right side of the interface, there is a navigation menu with examples of links to navigate, a list of sensors, a list of observations made by a sensor and its outputs. The navigation includes a quick list of links under the header “On this page section” to skip a section of the web page. The contents of the page can be sorted out by property. In the case of the sensors, the data can only be filtered by the type of sensor.

² <http://www.epimorphics.com/web/tools/elda.html>

The screenshot displays the 'Search Results' section of the Sant Cugat data portal. It features a list of six sensor types, each with a 'type' field containing its name:

- energea_2ndlightsconsumption**: type: Energea_2ndLightsConsumption
- energea_2ndtotalconsumption**: type: Energea_2ndTotalConsumption
- energea_3ndlightsconsumption**: type: Energea_3ndLightsConsumption
- energea_3ndtotalconsumption**: type: Energea_3ndTotalConsumption
- energea_acconsumption**: type: Energea_Ac consumption
- energea_co2**: type: Energea_Co2

On the right side, there are three utility panels:

- Navigate to**: A list of links: > List of sensors, > Observations of a sensor, > Output of a sensor.
- On This Page**: A list of links: > energea_2ndlightsconsumption, > energea_2ndtotalconsumption, > energea_3ndlightsconsumption, > energea_3ndtotalconsumption, > energea_acconsumption, > energea_co2, > energea_humidity, > energea_temperature1, > energea_temperature2, > energea_totalenergy, > next.
- Sort by**: A dropdown menu currently set to 'type'.
- View**: A breadcrumb trail: > Complete > all > basic > description > viewerMedium, and a dropdown menu currently set to 'type'.

Figure 17. Data portal environment. List of sensors

Figure 18 shows a web page that displays the output of a sensor, in particular of an energy consumption sensor. The main property of an output is “has value” which contains the energy consumed in a given period of time. At the bottom of the interface, there is the SPARQL query used to retrieve the data. This is especially useful to develop services that need that data.

energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410180000
Show Search Form

http://iarcdev.housing.salle.url.edu:8080/leida-common-1.3.13/sensoroutput/energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410180000

has value	0.491	< 🔍 >
type	Energy_ConsumptionSensorOutput	
is primary topic of	energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410180000.html?_view=Complete	

Navigate to ?

- > List of sensors
- > Observations of a sensor
- > Output of a sensor

View ?

- > Complete > all > basic > description
- > viewerMedium

- ★ has value
- ★ type
- ★ is primary topic of

Viewer

This is the SPARQL query that was generated to pull together the data that is provided about the selected item. You can modify it here and re-run the query but you may find more options at the endpoint's page.

```

PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX ssn: <http://purl.oclc.org/NET/ssnx/ssn#>
PREFIX time: <http://www.w3.org/2006/time#>
CONSTRUCT {?item ssn:featureOfInterest ?__0 .
?item ssn:observationResultTime ?__1 .
?__1 time:inXSDDateTime ?__2 .
?item ssn:observedProperty ?__3 .
?item ssn:observationResult ?__4 .
?__4 ssn:hasValue ?__5 .
?item ssn:hasValue ?__6 .
?item rdf:type ?__7 .
?item rdfs:label ?__8 .
?item ssn:observedBy ?__9 .
}
WHERE {
{ VALUES ?item {
<http://www.optimus-smartcity.eu/resource/sant_cugat/sensorou
}
}

```

Figure 18. Data portal environment. Sensor output

Figure 19 shows a list of observations made by an energy consumption sensor. Each observation has different properties such as the feature of interest, observation results (by clicking the link the user goes to the sensor output page shown in Figure 18), the time when the observation was made (observation result time), the sensor that made the observation (observed by), and the property observed.

Search Results
Show Search Form

energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410180000

feature of interest	energy_consumption
observation result	[energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410180000]
has value	0.491 < Q >
observation result time	[20150410180000]
in XSD date time	10/04/2015 18:00:00 < Q >
observed by	energea_3ndtotalconsumption
observed property	energy_consumption

energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410170000

feature of interest	energy_consumption
observation result	[energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410170000]
has value	0.689 < Q >
observation result time	[20150410170000]
in XSD date time	10/04/2015 17:00:00 < Q >
observed by	energea_3ndtotalconsumption
observed property	energy_consumption

energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410160000

feature of interest	energy_consumption
observation result	[energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410160000]
has value	0.701 < Q >

Navigate to ?

- > List of sensors
- > Observations of a sensor
- > Output of a sensor

On This Page ?

- > energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410180...
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- > energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410110...
- > energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410100...
- > energea_3ndtotalconsumption20150410090...
- > next >

Sort by ?

- feature of interest
- observation result > has value
- observation result time > in XSD date time
- observed by
- observed property

View ?

- > Complete > all > basic > description
- feature of interest
- observation result > has value
- observation result time > in XSD date time
- observed by
- observed property

Figure 19. Data portal environment. List of observations of a sensor

5 Conclusions

The OPTIMUS DSS environments provide monitored data, predicted data, and short-term action plans to different kind of users. The three environments that have been developed – end-user, management and data portal– are fully integrated with the other modules of the DSS (i.e., semantic framework, prediction models, and inference rules).

The environments have been designed with the collaboration of the end-users, who have taken part of the surveys and in the elaboration of the mock-ups carried out in Task 1.3. The successive versions of the interfaces have been discussed with the end-users. However, interface design is never a one-time process. The interfaces of the environments will need to be continuously validated with end-users and domain experts as the development of the OPTIMUS DSS progresses, particularly during the demonstration phase.

Further steps in the development of the interfaces will be taken after carrying out a usability test with the end-users using the final version of the DSS. This will be done along with the deployment of the DSS in the pilot cities. Taking into account to users' feedback, the interfaces will be enhanced, refined and further developed.